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Editor

Prof. (Dr.) RENU JOHRI

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Dance education in the K-12 curriculum: An NEP 2020 perspective with specific reference to Outcomes-based standards

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Abstract—Creative and aesthetic expression has been one of the important attributes of dance education in the curricular framework of NCERT. More recently, NEP 2020 has laid emphasis on experiential learning and has given importance to competency-based learning as one of the standard pedagogies within each subject. The learning outcomes-based frameworks have become an important proponent that leads towards achieving the competency standards both in learning and in assessment. Since arts have been made part of the multidisciplinary choice-based courses available for secondary school students, never before has there been a greater need for standards in art education, a pedagogical concept that has been a permanent feature in all other streams and subject areas. The paper has analysed various frameworks of learning outcomes and standards in dance and art education and has developed a model outcome standards with skill standards that can be applied to dance/art education. This is a primary move towards developing sequential process oriented skill standards in arts for all age groups of K-12. This research has utilized qualitative research with content analysis of empirical data and documents. It has relied mostly on primary data that have been available in the form of reports or policy documents of national bodies like NCERT or CBSE, talks and discussions by policymakers during the formal launch of NEP 2020 and other significant arts standard frameworks that have been adopted by countries like the USA. The outcome-based learning emphasised by various recent educational policies and the stress on competency standards by the NEP 2020 has put a lot of emphasis on recognising and implementing standards in learning especially in the case of arts education in India where it has been felt lacking. The paper has addressed this gap by developing a outcome-based skills standards model after comparisons and analysis of the available frameworks in arts education. This is the first step towards standardising process-oriented outcome-based learning in the context of Arts education in India.

Key Words: Arts education, K-12 arts curriculum, Dance education, learning outcomes, NEP 2020, standards in arts learning, content standards, outcome-based learning, competency-based learning.

Introduction—The new National Education Policy 2020 has been a path breaker in terms of bridging the chasm that has for years existed between the science streams normally considered scholastic and the art stream that was relegated to being co-scholastic. Overcoming the demarcations that had for years deprived the students of holistically multidisciplinary and choice-based education, it has initiated the transformation of the education system, to bring an integrated learning approach- more liberal and student-oriented. It is a much needed change to align with the standards in place around the world. This not only means a shift of the conventional emphasis to STEM subjects to become inclusive and give place to STEAM but also has brought in the importance of adopting the standards of teaching-learning pedagogy, both the prevalent and new, to be upheld to cater to the arts education too. New pedagogical methods and tools thus need to be made relevant to arts education too. This paper has studied NEP 2020's bearings on art education, the present status of arts education with respect to the new NCF foundational stage of 2022 and the other stages of the new academic structure of school education, the importance of outcome-based standards and learning outcomes for arts at different stages of learning. This apart, it has analysed the present position of dance in arts education, briefly compared NCERT's different frameworks of learning available in teaching dance,

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and developed a model of learning outcomes framework and its corresponding skill standards expected of students that can be made applicable for subject specific cognitive and practical levels.

With an emphasis on K-12, the objectives of this paper are to study and

1. Examine the importance and scope of NEP 2020 to arts education
1. Understand the significance of outcome-based standards in arts
2. Analyse the available frameworks of learning standards in the instructional design of dance education
3. Steps to implement performance/ process based learning outcomes as a necessity for dance education
4. Create a model of learning outcomes framework with skill standards based on art processes

Aspects of developing an Arts standards and pedagogical framework for teaching -learning of arts education for school children has been an area that has seen very little research in the Indian context. This work has relied mostly on primary data in the form of reports or policy documents of national bodies like NCERT or CBSE, talks and discussions by policy makers during the formal launch of NEP 2020 and other significant arts standard frameworks that have been adopted by countries like the USA. The paper has used qualitative research with content analysis of empirical data and documents. The limitations of the study lie in the number international frameworks of art/dance education that have been analysed. As only the DBAE, NCCAS and VPA content standards of the USA have been looked at apart from the Indian policy papers of NCERT, CBSE and Azim Premji University, a few more from the eastern hemisphere would have also provided a comparative view of the constituents in the skills standards frame.

NEP 2020- Bearings on Arts education—The NEP 2020 has clearly spelt out that there shall be no hard demarcations between arts and sciences, between curricular and extra-curricular activities, between vocational, academic and professional streams, etc. in order to eliminate harmful hierarchies, silos among disciplines and between different areas of learning. The undoing of the silos between different areas of learning thereby promotes multi-disciplinarity which is one of the principles of NEP 2020 and aims at providing interdisciplinary grounds, giving scope for holistic learning and promoting art-based inquiry. It meant that the importance of art education has shifted from being co-scholastic to being at par with scholastic. The preservation and promotion of Indian Arts and culture are considered important contributors to raising the quality of the higher education system as it was felt that qualities like empathy, human values, and creativity are best developed through arts. With an emphasis on experiential learning, art integration as a cross-curricular pedagogical approach has been stressed in school education to create joyful classrooms and for imbibing the Indian ethos through the integration of Indian art and culture in the teaching and learning process at every level.

In the section on the promotion of Indian languages, arts, and culture in the NEP 2020 document, cultural awareness and expression are among the major competencies considered important to develop in children, in order to provide them with a sense of identity, belonging, as well as an appreciation of other cultures and identities. The arts, besides strengthening cultural identity and awareness, and uplifting societies, are well known to enhance cognitive and creative abilities in individuals from early childhood onwards. And as a measure to make this possible, the provision to hire outstanding local artists, writers, crafts persons, and other experts as specialised instructors in various subjects of local expertise at schools and HEIs has been emphasised.

NEP 2020 and Outcome-based Standards: Overview & Importance—Among the few approaches, the new NEP 2020 emphatically stressed the importance of learner outcomes in the curriculum framework with reference to curricular and learner expectations. The thrust here is on outcome-based learning and the curriculum that is aligned with the learning outcomes. There is also a strong emphasis on competency-based learning to effectively provide skills or an application-based outlook to the learning undertaken. Apart from this is the emphasis on the outcomes-based assessment by which competency-based learning

and its outcome can be linked directly to the assessment undertaken. Thereby the simultaneous thrusts on three interlinked areas in the educational approach including learner outcomes, competency-based learning and outcome-based assessment all lead towards adopting content standards in learning or creating standards in content which are relevant and aligned with the processes of gaining the knowledge of the subject and not just remain only subject-based. Content standards which are process or performance-based derived from pedagogical levels of learning are relevant and purposeful for teaching-learning and assessment. The first determinant for implementing CBE (competency-based education), according to the recently published learning framework created by Azim Premji University in collaboration with CBSE for classes 9 and 10, is a curriculum which is aligned to 'defined learning outcomes that clearly state the competencies to be achieved' (2022).

NEP 2020 assessment reforms recommended a shift from content based assessment to competency based assessment with emphasis on testing high order thinking skills, based on achievement of essential learning outcomes or acquiring minimal standards of competence. This draws our focus to developing outcomes based assessment that is inevitable where the outcomes are more than just content specific. They are to be competency or performance specific. The learning processes or skills that are the levels of cognition as in Bloom's taxonomy (Bloom,1956; Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001) or the levels of the psychomotor domain as in Dave (1967), Simpson (1972) or Harrow's (1972) taxonomy that have catered to strategically plan the teaching and learner expectations, are to be engaged in setting standards of content. The learning outcomes actualized in terms of these levels of the taxonomy need not play out individually or selectively according to the specificities of the contents but rather operate as standardized levels according to the age of the student and play out evenly as taxonomical gradation against the topics. The learning outcomes for each subject are expressed in terms of cognitive skills to be demonstrated and the content to be acquired by the students.

Approach to Dance Education in School Curriculum: Points to ponder –Dance as an art form plays a very important role in the holistic development of an individual and is considered an essential component of a comprehensive education particularly among school children. Dance education, as Koff (2000) states, “does not have complex mastery as its goal. Rather it enables every child, regardless of physical capabilities, to be expressive in a non-verbal manner- to explore and incorporate the physical self as a functional part of the whole social being”. The terms “dance education” and “dance training” she opines, are to be differentiated and not interchanged as they imply different goals. Dance education does not seek to prepare children to become performers whereas dance training aims at mastery of skill and future performance. And for this, as Bonbright (1999) rightly points out, it is imperative for art instructors to be both artists and educators. It is as educators that they understand the content, process, the methodology of developing and delivering curricula, syllabi and assessments. McColl's four steps inherent in making dance a viable part of arts experiences suggests that it is important that teachers (1) recognize and understand dance for children as an art form, (2) be able to articulate the relationship of dance to the other arts and to the basic learning process, (3) approach dance as arts educators- not just as teachers of movement, and (4) accept the challenge of including aesthetic elements in the selection of lesson content and in the structure of the learning process” (1979).

Arts Education- Study and evaluation of the present status with reference to NEP 2020–The document, *Early childhood care and education: Foundations of learning NEP 2020*, talks about multifaceted play -based, inquiry based learning with a focus on cognitive, affective, psychomotor abilities along with early literacy and numeracy for children in the foundational stages that is from 3 years till the age of 8 years where learning is supposedly to be multilevel play and activity-based learning (Fig 1).

Fig 1 Early childhood care and education

Source: <https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/shikshak-parv/P1.pdf>

The recent National curriculum framework made available for the children of the foundational stage (NCERT,2022) brings its focus on foundational literacy and numeracy. The major domains presented pertain to physical development, socio-emotional and ethical development, cognitive development, language and literacy development, aesthetic and cultural development and positive learning habits. The subject of arts is brought under the domain of aesthetic and cultural development with the following curricular goals and competencies (Table 1)

Table 1

Curricular goals and competencies in arts education in NCF Foundational stage

<i>Domain</i>	
Aesthetic and Cultural Development	
<i>Curricular goals</i>	
CG-12 -Children develop abilities and sensibilities in visual and performing arts and express their emotions through art in meaningful and joyful ways	
<i>Competencies</i>	
C-12.1	Explores and plays with a variety of materials and tools to create two-dimensional and three-dimensional artworks in varying sizes
C-12.2	Explores and plays with own voice, body, spaces, and a variety of objects to create music, role-play, dance and movement.
C-12.3	Innovates and works imaginatively to express a range of ideas and emotions through the arts
C-12.4	Works collaboratively in the arts
C-12.5	Communicates and appreciates a variety of responses while creating and experiencing different forms of art, local culture, and heritage

Some observations on the NCF Foundational stage, 2022

The subject domains and learning domains have been mixedly placed under the common head of domains leading to an overlap of both. The subject of arts including the performing and visual arts have been slotted under the domain -aesthetic and cultural development in the foundational stage (refer fig 1). Arts when put under a separate subject-oriented domain has highly restricted its scope to be only understood with reference to aesthetic and cultural sphere of development. It has been segregated from those of common learning domains like physical and motor development or cognitive development or socio-emotional and ethical development and in doing so has made it appear as if arts have nothing to do with these common learning domains. This superficial demarcation where the learning and subject oriented domains have been mixed up has further segregated the STEM subjects from arts as none of the other domains is subject-specific as arts have been portrayed here. This problem can be illustrated best with the following instances from the other domains which are very relevant to the competencies of the subject area of dance. These limitations in the foundational stage essentially again demarcate the scope of arts in the education set-up.

Some of the domains and competencies relevant to arts that are found to overlap with the competencies of the learning domains are identified below:

Physical Development

CG-3 Children develop a fit and flexible body

Competencies

C-3.1 Shows coordination between sensorial perceptions and body movements in various activities

C-3.2 Shows balance, coordination, and flexibility in various physical activities

C-3.3 Shows precision and control in working with their hands and fingers

C-3.4 Shows strength and endurance in carrying, walking, and running

Socio-Emotional and Ethical Development

CG-4 Children develop emotional intelligence

Competencies

C-4.2 Recognises different emotions and makes deliberate efforts to regulate them appropriately

C-4.3 Interacts comfortably with other children and adults

C-4.4 Shows cooperative behaviour with other children

Dance in Arts education- Analysis of frameworks of learning outcomes

The syllabus of arts education, NCERT 2008 with regard to frameworks of learning shows that content-based learning had been followed in the case of Dance education

- Till class five, integrated learning approach was used where usage of arts was in a composite way with a common framework for classes I-V. The learner expectations or learning outcomes are found to be specifically according to the contents and did not correspond to the levels of cognitive or psychomotor development to which it could be attributed to
- For upper primary classes (VI-VIII) and secondary classes (IX-X), the syllabus of arts education widened to include varied domains of performing arts like theatre, music and dance and the visual arts. This too is a content oriented framework. It included a common list of fourteen learning outcomes which were content and class based learning outcomes (dance: VI -VIII).

With reference to the Learning indicators and learning outcomes, NCERT (2014), common learning outcomes are suggested for every subject at each school stage. Examining the curricular expectations and learner outcomes of arts education in Middle school (earlier called as upper-primary (VI-VIII) shows that

common outcome based curricular areas were delineated for arts in general with specific learning outcomes provided under each area for every art form. These learning outcomes were found to be mostly process oriented in the case of visual arts, theatre and music but not so in the case of dance where it majorly retained only the components of content. The learner outcomes as processes too were content specific without reflecting the levels of learning or cognition and therefore provided inadequate sequential standards in the learning outcomes.

An example of a curricular expectation and its corresponding learning outcome is given below in tables 2 & 3

<p>Curricular expectation- To develop artistic skills</p>	<p>Curricular expectation - Understand basics of different art forms of Dance</p>
<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expressing through hand and finger movement • Use of gestures or mudras • Stylish feet movement • Combining all artistic skills 	<p>Learning Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warm up movements to prepare the learner for dance • Alert mind • Balance of the body for an aesthetic posture required in dance • Flexible body to be able to create many types of movement • Use of all parts of the body to express creatively, aesthetically

Table 2

Table 3

Another document ‘Learning outcomes for Elementary stage’ by NCERT, 2016, did not have recommended outcomes for the subject of arts education.

Developing and Determining Learning Outcomes Framework

If learner outcomes continue to be dependent on the contents of the subject, the question of recognising stages of learning and cognition is selective upon the chosen theme and content and if there are to be standards to be upheld in every subject that is dealt with, the learning processes need to tag their line with effective stages of learning. The latest continuous and comprehensive evaluation (CCE) document (2019), states that “the pedagogy employed to accomplish the desired goals of learning, should be such that it emphasises the processes of learning specific to each curricular area”. The present practice of content/curriculum based learner outcome thus has to change its focus to process based learning outcome where content areas are to be redesignated as domains that are largely major learning processes and specific learning outcomes too are to reflect sequential process standards. Such a framework would provide standards in learning outcomes for every topic or content in a subject and also help to offer a standardised frame of learning outcomes which can be adopted and adapted for every class.

Learning Outcomes and their Skill Standards for Dance / Arts Education for K-12: A Model

A model framework of outcomes and their skill standards has been arrived at after analysing various frameworks of art standards. The learning outcomes, based on levels of cognitive, and psychomotor skills development, may be understood and known as standards of content or learning outcome standards and are illustrated through the stages of

Perceiving/knowing, Creating (presenting/performing), Reasoning/Analysing, Associating, Connecting

The learning outcomes and their corresponding skills:

1. **Perceiving/knowing**- identifies, distinguishes, imitates, demonstrates
2. **Creating (presenting/performing)**- conceptualises, designs, refines, revises, performs
3. **Reasoning/analysing**- perceives, organises, analyses, responds, interprets, evaluates
4. **Associating**- understands, contextualises
5. **Connecting**- integrates, applies

The next stage of this would be to create content/ domain-specific learning outcomes and indicators by linking the contents in the content domain to the learner outcome where every content domain need not be represented by all stages of the learner outcomes

Conclusion—The NEP 2020 has been a milestone in terms of bridging the divide between the curricular and co-curricular subjects under which dance and other arts had till now been marginalised in the education system. This shift shall become a rewarding experience for the students in K-12 in the sense of opportunities for holistic growth. However, as art educators, it becomes binding to outgrow our reclusiveness in adapting to new pedagogical approaches which arts education till now has been slow to catch up to. The analysis undertaken in this research has pulled up some dormant strings in the educational framework that till now had not been addressed. This has concerned the articulation of learning outcomes with due importance to theoretical levels of cognitive and psychomotor/ practical skill-based learning approaches that have been available to us as taxonomies of learning. The frameworks that have been formulated based on different studies undertaken help to provide stage specific/ sequential knowledge that has become a mandatory prerequisite for a scientific based pedagogy. Adapting such parameters in teaching-learning of arts especially dance has been found lacking in the national frameworks. This continues to be the situation even post-NEP 2020 as the paper has shown that the arts have been segregated under the subject domain of arts and cultural development in the newly formulated NCF foundational learning where it exists exclusive of the three common domains of learning. Looking at art with a coloured lens to be only capable of serving the purpose of cultural and artistic development of kids has resulted in a separate sphere when other subjects are not shown so and are prioritised to have all three aspects of learning. This shows the inadequacies still prevalent with regard to adapting the art pedagogies to new standard approaches and doing away with the silos that according to NEP 2020 have to be prevented from forming between subjects. The scope of aesthetic expressions has to go hand in hand with its learning to grow in a creative way as has been emphasised by NCERT and not subsist on cultural development which may be understood as one of its many domains. It may also be noted that though arts have a higher creative component as compared to other subject areas, it possesses cognitive and psychomotor components in an equally important way. The paper is a step in this direction to imprint the new pedagogical approaches upheld by the recent NEP, which includes competency and outcome-driven standards, to be available in learning and assessment in arts education in the country. The model of learning outcomes with skill standards for arts education developed after comparison and analysis of various other frameworks is a step towards this direction.

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